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Reference Documents

RD#	Doc Number	Issue	Date	Document Title
1	IAC-16-B6.1.2	-	-	Operations Data Files Driving Force Behind International Space Station Operations
2	SSP-50252	Rev. P	March 2015	International Space Station program Operations Data File management Plan
3	N/A	5.0	March 2015	ESA ODF Management Plan
4	SSP 50313	Rev. E	September 2014	Display and Graphics Commonality Standard
5	D3.X	0.5	2017-05-24	ISPR Design Document
6	H2020 BIOWYSE deliverable D3.1	Issue 1	March 2018	Breadboard detailed Design and Development.

Executive Summary

The EDEN ISS project is aimed at testing key technologies in view of space operations. The Mobile Test Facility represents a platform to verify the possibility to manage plant growth and safe food production in extreme conditions. But the race to space is done of small steps having the objective to reach intermediates goals, like for example the understanding on how the plants can be grown and managed in a closed ambient and with conditions that are different from those experience on hearth (for example under low gravity conditions, with artificial lighting conditions, etc).

That includes the verification and the validation of the technical solutions that have to be designed to work in these conditions. For example the distribution of water and nutrients to the plants is a critical items in the absence of gravity, because the water, the air and the nutrient solutions distribute in different way. Several experiments are therefore required to increase the knowledge of the plant and system behaviour in space and to solve all the technical uncertainties in order to be ready for a complex mission that foresees the production of food on an extra-terrestrial outpost.

For that reason, in the EDEN ISS project, a small laboratory has been implemented as first step on the way that to design and realize a scientific payload for plant experiments on board of the ISS.

This laboratory, called RUCOLA (Rack-like Unit for Consistent on-Orbit Leafy crops Availability), has been designed looking at a future integration in the new version of the European Drawer Rack (EDR MKII) on board of the Columbus, the European Module of the International Space Station.

The present document has the scope to follow-up the lessons learnt from the laboratory and the Antarctica test campaigns by outlining the following aspects:

- Identification of the preliminary architecture of a plant growth rack-size experiment on the ISS – the RUCOLA system (Chapter 1)
- Identification of the RUCOLA flight system preliminary physical configuration (Chapter 2)
- Preliminary identification of the ISS test objectives and derivation of the flight operations, including a preliminary list of the activities to be performed by ISS astronauts and ground operators (Chapter 3)
- Identification of the RUCOLA products to be used for on board operations and the related development processes (Chapter 4)
- Identification of a possible setup of a control centre and its connection to the ISS ground network, including the tools required for the RUCOLA remote operations (Chapter 5)
- Identification of a set of relevant aspects related to growing plants on-board ISS (Chapter 7)

The design stage is not mature enough to already develop detailed flight operational procedures or to develop tools for RUCOLA remote operations (as matter of fact the operations preparations, including the setup of the ground segment, starts from the phase C/D of a project, and we are pretty far from this phase). For this reason this document focuses on the analysis of the operations scenario, with the description of the on board and remote activities, in order to correctly define the operations requirements in view of a future development of the RUCOLA Flight Unit.

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Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation	Acronym	Explanation
C&DH	Command and Data Handling	MMS	Microbial Monitoring Module
CD-MCS	Columbus Decentralised Mission Control System	MTF	Mobile Test facility
CFU	Compact Filter Unit	NDS	Nutrient Delivery System
CGS	Columbus Ground Support	NMS	Nutrient Management System
COL CC	Columbus Control Center	ODF	Operations Data File
COTS	Commercial Off The Shelf	P/L	Payload
DaSS	Data Services System	PC&DH	Power Command and Data Handling
DAU	Data Acquisition Unit	PODF	Payload Operations Data File
DI-Water	Deionized Water	POIC	Payload Operations Integration Centre
EAC	European Astronaut Center	QD	Quick disconnect
EC	Electrical Conductivity	RH	Relative Humidity
EDD	Event Driven Delivery	RM	Root Module
EDR	European Drawer Rack	SRM	Science Reference Model
EDR	European Drawer Rack	SW	Software
EI	Experimental inserts	TAS-I	Thales Alenia Space Italia
EM	Engineering Model	TBC	To Be Confirmed
ESA	European Space Agency	TBD	To Be Defined
FEG	Future Exploration Greenhouse	TC	Telecommands
GC-ACM	Growth Chamber Atmosphere Control Module	TCCS	Trace contaminants control system
GCM	Growth Chamber Module	TEC	Thermo-electric cooler
GEM	Gas Exchange Module	THC	Temperature and humidity control system
HW	Hardware	TM	Telemetries
IDAGS	Integrated Display and Graphics Standards	TPZ	Telespazio
IGS-network	Interconnected Ground Sub Network	TRL	Technology readiness level
ILS	Illumination System	UHB	User Home Base
ISPR	International Standard Payload Rack	USOC	User Support Operations Center
ISS	International Space Station	UV	Ultra Violet
LED	Light Emitting Diode	ViDS	Video Distribution and Conferencing System
MCC-H	Mission Control Center – Houston	VoCS	Voice Conferencing System
MCCM	Microbial Contamination Control Module	VPN	Virtual Private Network
MCC-M	Mission Control Centre – Moscow	WAN	Wide Area Network
MCCS	Major constituents control system		

1 Flight System Functional Architecture

The functional architecture of the system was only partially defined in RD5, with main focus on the fluidic loops.

The RUCOLA preliminary fluidic block diagram from the previous phase is reported in **Figure 1**. The nutrient solution mixing and distribution loop is represented by a black solid line, while the air circulation and quality control loop is represented by a light blue solid line. The external cooling loop is not represented (mentioned only for cooling of the thermo-electric cooler in the Temperature and Humidity Control Unit – THCU). The diagram is explained in RD3 section 4.1.

Figure 1: RUCOLA preliminary fluidic block diagram from previous project phase

The architecture was further studied with the following objectives:

- Review the identified fluidic loops functional architecture against results obtained previously (e.g. photo-ozonolysis breadboard test results) and possible new requirements emerged from the operational analysis activity
- Assess the cooling loop preliminary architecture
- Assess the power, command and data handling preliminary architecture

The results are summarized in the following subsections.

1.1 Operational fluid loops functional architecture

The operational fluid loops (thus excluding cooling water loop) functional architecture presented in Figure 1 was further elaborated in order to be in line with the current project status.

The updated fluidic block diagram is reported in Figure 2. All the changes with respect to the previous phase are highlighted as per figure caption.

The changes are described in the following table.

Table 1: RUCOLA fluidic block diagram changes from previous phase

ID	Affected Unit	Change description	Reason for change
1	MCCMU-L	Photo-ozonolysis unit changed to Microbial control unit in the return line of the recovered nutrient solution. (from the Root Module to the diluted nutrient solution tank)	UV unit was not tested in the previous phase. Alternative technologies for bacteria load control in the return nutrient solution need to be analysed. Currently, the necessary technology is not consolidated.
2	MCCMU-L	MiDASS system changed to not identified Microbe-specific monitoring unit	ESA MiDASS procurement is currently on-hold
3	NMU and MCCMU-L	Added 4 sampling ports for multiple liquids sample collection	To comply with operations identified in Chapter 3
4	Root Module	Multiple changes	See para 5.1.1
5	MCCMU-A	Second UV unit changed to HEPA	See para 5.3.1

Figure 2: RUCOLA updated fluidic block diagram (changes marked with #)

1.2 Cooling loop preliminary architecture

The current project assumption is that cooling water is provided from the rack hosting the P/L. As an example, the targeted EDR MKII facility can provide up to 180 L/h of cooling water with a temperature in the range 16-20°C.

Although the flight unit preliminary design activity of the previous phase was focusing on the 3 key module (NM, RM, MCCM), some assumption was made also concerning the cooling water utilization in the other modules. The identified uses of cooling water are summarized in the table below.

Table 2: Identified uses of cooling water

Module of interest	Cooling of cold plate in...	Notes
Growth Chamber Module	Thermo-electric cooler of growth chamber air loop	A thermo-electric cooler is likely going to be employed for latent and sensible heat removal from growth chamber atmosphere
Light Interception Module	Crop illumination LED panel	Although highly efficient, LEDs require efficient heat removal
Microbial Contamination Control Module – Liquid Loop	UV-LED water disinfection unit	UV-LEDs life strongly benefits by operating below 25°C
Microbial Contamination Control Module – Air Loop	UV-LED air disinfection unit late	UV-LEDs life strongly benefits by operating below 25°C
Microbial Contamination Control Module - Monitoring	Thermo-electric cooler of monitoring units reactants storage	Some reactant for ATP-metry (e.g. DENDRIDIAG) need to be stored at -20°C to increase time between replacements
Nutrient Module	Nutrient management drawer	The heat produced mainly by pumps and solenoid valves in the drawer need to be removed
n/a	Power, command and data handling drawer	The heat produced mainly by DC/Dc converters in the drawer need to be removed

Figure 3 in the next page describes a cooling loop preliminary architecture, starting from the above presented assumptions.

The figure below describes a cooling loop preliminary architecture. The system has been divided into drawers (or lockers, TBD) as per consideration reported in Chapter 2.

Remark: the path followed by the cooling water is currently arbitrary, since no thermal analysis was performed in support to its definition.

Figure 3: RUCOLA Preliminary Cooling Loop Block Diagram

Cooling water is provided by the rack supporting the RUCOLA P/L. The nutrient management drawer drives via an internal fan to the cold plate the heat generated mainly from the multiple pumps. The power, command and data handling drawer does the same with heat generated mainly by the DC/DC converters. The Microbial contamination control drawer has multiple units directly on cold plates, as well as the illumination drawer. In the growth chamber drawer both the air disinfection unit and the main heat exchanger of the growth chamber air loop are placed on cold plates. The main heat exchanger collects sensible and latent heat from the root and shoot zone, as well as from the active HW in the air loop.

1.3 Power, command and data handling system preliminary architecture

The RUCOLA power, command and data handling system will include two main subsystems:

- The Power Distribution Assembly (PDA)
- The Avionics System (AS)

The two subsystems are preliminary described as follows.

Power Distribution Assembly (PDA)

The PDA delivers power to the RUCOLA drawers. The PDA is powered via the EDR MK II power interface and provides the appropriate voltages to RUCOLA components. The PDA consists of input/output power connectors, a data connector, Electromagnetic Interference (EMI) filters, Direct Current to Direct Current (DC-DC) converters, and a microprocessor board. It provides 5V, 12V, 24V, and 28V power as required by the subsystems, and under program control, can individually turn each subsystem on or off.

Avionics System (AS)

RUCOLA has three command and data management components: the graphical user interfaces, the power, command and data handling drawer (PCDH) processor, and microcontrollers distributed into the other drawers for some of the RUCOLA subsystems (e.g. the UVC disinfection unit, the ATP monitoring unit, the MiDASS system as a minimum). The Illumination drawer also contains three COTS cameras, designed to operate autonomously or via ground commands, for capturing still images.

There are two RUCOLA GUI interfaces, one that resides on the RUCOLA Laptop Computer (RLC) and one that resides on a Ground Science Station which allows a ground operator to control the RUCOLA remotely. The GUI interface on the RLC provides the crew with visibility into PFPU systems as well as a secondary or backup command and control option. Each GUI displays real-time experiment data and APH health and status data. Operators are able to issue commands to adjust the experiment control parameters, turn components on or off as necessary to facilitate experiment maintenance and initiate the recording and downloading of images of the experiment's progress. The GUI receives its data from and sends its commands to the PCDH.

PCDH is the Avionics computer that controls the environment of the RUCOLA Growth Chamber, records all imagery associated with the experiment, records all data about the experiment and hardware status, and transmits that information to the GUI where the data is displayed. The PCDH evaluates the measured conditions in the Growth Chamber against the environmental settings provided by the user in order to provide commands to the RUCOLA microcontrollers to maintain or change the environment. All imagery is stored locally on the PCDH and made available for download by a GUI operator. PCDH also provides specific health indicators (i.e. heartbeat) to the EDR MKII Rack which controls the emergency safing of RUCOLA.

Figure 4 reports a preliminary architecture of RUCOLA power, command and data handling system.

As visible below, a set of units have its own electronics within the drawer where it is operational. This is done mainly for units expected to work with a digital signal, such as the UV LED units, the LED illumination lamp, the cameras, the microbial monitoring units and the root module multi parameters soil sensors.

Controllers of high power consumption hardware (TEC and heaters) are preliminary configured within the PCDH drawer in order to have a proper thermal and EMC control.

Figure 4: RUCOLA power, command and data handling system preliminary architecture

2 Flight System Preliminary Physical Architecture

The **physical architecture** of the RUCOLA system was further analyzed, aiming at defining the following aspects of the PFPU system:

- ROM mass
- ROM power consumption
- ROM water cooling loop load
- ROM volume
- Compatibility with a flight opportunity on the ISS (baseline on European Drawer Rack MK II, backup on Express rack)

This exercise is needed for identification of the PFPU IOD strategy.

The results is presented and a ROM evaluation of the related budgets is summarized in the following subsections.

RD5 identifies and describes the following RUCOLA process specific modules, the starting point for the identification of the suggested **physical architecture**:

- Root Module (RM) – root and tuber zone management
- Nutrient Module (NM) – nutrient management
- Microbial Contamination Control Module (MCCM) – microbial environment management
- Light Interception Module (LIM) – crop illumination management
- Growth Chamber Module (GCM) – shoot zone management
- Gas Exchange Module (GEM) – atmosphere revitalization management

Considerations toward a physical architecture

The following considerations were made in support to the preliminary **physical architecture** outlining (already performed at Antarctica demonstrator development level):

- Some of the above listed modules need to be physically enclosed into a single experimental insert (i.e. drawer or locker). As an example, the RM and GCM need to be physically interconnected to host the plant root and shoot zone.
- It is more straightforward to design an independent drawer/locker for the NM (with only 1/8"-1/4" fluidic lines as interface with the RM) and the LIM (with the only requirements of being able to deliver light to the GCM), than for the GEM (with bigger air ducts as interface with the GCM).
- Since the MCCM controls the microbial environment of the nutrient solution loop as well as of the air loop, multiple solutions are possible:
 - Atmosphere microbial contamination reduction components are more likely to be co-placed with the GEM

- Nutrient solution/recovered condensate microbial contamination reduction components are more likely to be co-placed with the NM
- Microbial contamination on-line monitoring technologies can be placed into an independent drawer/locker (with minimal fluidic interfaces for the gas/liquid samples)
- Power, command and data handling functions need to be considered in addition to the functions already included in the above mentioned process specific modules; although an independent unit with centralized functions is likely to be selected, some of such functions can be partially distributed among the different above mentioned units
- The HW should be divided among multiple drawers/lockers for the following reasons:
 - an incremental PFPU on-orbit integration is possible to support a module-specific demonstration, as a risk mitigation strategy
 - the PFPU is likely going to occupy up to one full rack, there is no known plan to deliver to the ISS any more complete racks, so the P/L will need to fit into cargo bags

2.1 ROM volume and compatibility with a flight opportunity

Starting from the above considerations, the following preliminary physical division of the RUCOLA system into drawers/lockers was generated:

- Power, command and data handling drawer - 720x420x90 mm³
- Nutrient management drawer (incl. NM and MCCM portion related to reduction of contamination in the liquid loops) - 720x420x265 mm³
- Growth chamber drawer (incl. RM, GCM, GEM and MCCM portion related to reduction of contamination in the growth chamber air loop) - 720x420x400 mm³
- Illumination drawer dedicated to the LIM - 720x420x420 mm³
- Microbial monitoring drawer (incl. technologies for specific and a-specific selected microbial monitoring solutions - 720x420x180 mm³

Figure 5 shows a preliminary image of RUCOLA flight demonstrator as an Experimental Insert (EI) of the European Drawer Rack (EDR) MK II. The image was generated capitalizing the design experience gained throughout the previous phase Antarctica demonstrator lessons learnt.

The five identified RUCOLA drawers/lockers have been arranged within the EDR MK II rack in order to fully occupy the left bay (the largest one) with all the units except the microbial monitoring one. This disposition will support a step wise demonstration of the system initially also without the MiDASS and ATP measurement systems. Moreover, since the microbial monitoring drawer design is the most uncertain, this disposition shall provide sufficient margin for its re-sizing.

The Illumination drawer is obviously placed on top of the growth chamber drawer, while the nutrient management drawer is placed beneath it, closer to the root zone. The power, command and data

handling drawer is preliminary placed in the bottom of the four drawers stack, but nothing prevents to move it to the top of it. A more detailed configuration effort is necessary to freeze this disposition.

The thermal control system (TCS) is visible as two columns on the sides of the growth chamber drawer. The below image shows a design version with redounded TCS (two equal columns), which is a possible evolution of the preliminary design proposed in Chapter 1, pending a more detailed analysis of acceptable risks for the IOD activity.

Figure 5: Preliminary image of RUCOLA flight demonstrator as an Experimental Insert (EI) of the European Drawer Rack (EDR) MK II

The following paragraphs present a ROM evaluation of the RUCOLA flight demonstrator budgets. The source of the data for all the subsystems that were not analyzed as flight design is the RUCOLA system Antarctica demonstrator [RD 5].

2.2 ROM mass

Table 3 reports the RUCOLA flight demonstrator mass ROM evaluation results.

Table 3: RUCOLA flight demonstrator mass ROM evaluation results

Subsystem	Mass (kg)	Notes/ Reference
Power, command and data handling drawer	15	
Drawer	5	[RD 5] ¹
Power conversion assy	3	[RD 5]
Data management assy	7	[RD 5] ²
Nutrient management drawer	23	
Drawer	6	[RD 5] ¹
Nutrient Module	15	[RD 5]
MCCM – liquids contamination mitigation	2	[RD 5]
Growth chamber drawer	27	
Growth Chamber Module (incl. drawer)	14	[RD 5] ¹
Root Module	2	[RD 5]
MCCM – air contamination mitigation	2	[RD 5]
Gas Exchange Module (incl. THC)	9	[RD 5] ²
Illumination drawer	16	
Drawer	41	[RD 5] ¹
Illumination Module	11	[RD 5] ²
Observation cameras	1	[RD 5]
Microbial monitoring drawer	15	
Drawer	5	May be partially redundant since other units also have secondary structures
ATP measurement system	5	[RD 6] ¹
MiDASS-like system	5	Assumed same as ATP sys.
TOTAL	96	

¹ design toward launch loads open

² margin of improvement since missing optimization for space flight

2.3 ROM power consumption

Table 4 reports the RUCOLA flight demonstrator peak power consumption ROM evaluation results.

Table 4: RUCOLA flight demonstrator peak power consumption ROM evaluation results

Subsystem	Peak Power (W)	Notes/ Reference
Power, command and data handling drawer	80	
Power conversion assy	10	[RD 5] ¹
Data management assy	70	[RD 5] ¹
Nutrient management drawer	40	
Nutrient Module	34	[RD 5] ¹
MCCM – liquids contamination mitigation	6	[RD 5]
Growth chamber drawer	200	
Growth Chamber Module	0	[RD 5]
Root Module	15	[RD 5] ¹
MCCM – air contamination mitigation	10	[RD 5]
Gas Exchange Module (incl. THC)	175	[RD 5] ¹
Illumination drawer	110	
Illumination Module	100	[RD 5] ¹
Observation cameras	10	[RD 5] ¹
Microbial monitoring drawer	100	
ATP measurement system	50	[RD 6] ¹
MiDASS-like system	50	Assumed same as ATP sys.
TOTAL	530	

¹ margin of improvement since based partially on COTS equipment first iteration

2.4 ROM water cooling loop thermal load

The cooling loop preliminary architecture is presented in para. 1.2. Starting from Table 2, Table 5 reports the preliminary evaluated thermal loads to EDR MK II cooling water loop.

Table 5: Water cooling loop thermal load preliminary evaluation

Cooling of cold plate in...	Thermal load (W)	Ref. / Note
Thermo-electric cooler of growth chamber air loop	117.5	2.4.1 (calculated)
Crop illumination LED panel	54.1	2.4.2 (calculated)
MCCM Drawer	100	8.2 (same as power consumption)
Nutrient Management Drawer	40	8.2 (same as power consumption)
Power, Command and Data Handling Drawer	80	8.2 (same as power consumption)
TOTAL	391.6	~400 W

2.4.1 Thermo-electric cooler of growth chamber air loop

Table 6 reports the growth chamber thermal load evaluation in the worst case scenario (full canopy, day-time). The calculation of the sensible heat from the crop illumination LED lamp to shoot zone is detailed in Table 8. Latent heat released from the full canopy was calculated assuming 0.16 g/h-m² of water vapor production (from RD 13). This heat is sequestered by the plant from the sensible heat introduced by the illumination.

Table 6: Growth chamber thermal load evaluation – worst case scenario (full canopy, day-time)

Parameter	Power [W]
Sensible heat from LED lamp to shoot zone	45.9
Latent heat from plants	24.1
Sensible heat sequestered by plant evapotranspiration	-24.1
Sensible heat from fan, sensors and UV LED to air loop	15.0
Total sensible heat introduced into air loop	36.8
Total latent heat introduced into air loop	24.1

An online psychrometric tool (<http://www.sugartech.co.za/psychro/>) was then used in support to the evaluation of the heat load to the thermo-electric cooler of growth chamber air loop. The calculations are briefly summarized and justified in Table 7.

Table 7: Summary of the evaluation of the heat load to the thermo-electric cooler of growth chamber air loop

Parameter	Unit	Value	Note
Target			
Air Temperature	[°C]	23±1.5	Set-point
Air Relative Humidity	[%]	70±5	Set-point
Volumetric Flow	[m ³ /h]	34.6	Calculated to guarantee temperature range
Air volume exchangers	[vol/min]	6	Calculated from volumetric flow using shoot zone volume
Flow speed in shoot zone	[cm/s]	6	Calculated (target 1-20) using shoot zone cross surface
Air inlet (target)			
Air Temperature	[°C]	21.5	From set-point
Air water vapor fraction	[g/kg]	11.9	From set-point
Air Relative Humidity	[%]	74	Calculated w/Tool
Enthalpy	[kJ/kg]	51.6	Calculated w/Tool
Air outlet (target)			
Air Temperature	[°C]	24.5	From set-point
Air water vapor fraction	[g/kg]	12.8	From set-point
Air Relative Humidity	[%]	66	Calculated w/Tool
Enthalpy	[kJ/kg]	57.2	Calculated w/Tool
Dehumidification/cooling			
Air water vapor fraction	[g/kg]	11.9	Same as air inlet
Humidity	[%]	100%	Set to have dehumidification
Temperature	[°C]	16.7	Calculated w/Tool
Enthalpy	[kJ/kg]	46.9	Calculated w/Tool
Required cooling power	[W]	117.5	Calculated as difference between air outlet enthalpy and dehumidification/cooling enthalpy
Heating (after dehumidification)			
Heating power	[W]	55.6	Calculated to reheat air to air inlet target

2.4.2 Crop illumination LED panel cold plate

Table 8 summarizes crop illumination LED lamp cooling calculations starting from the RUCOLA Antarctica demonstrator lamp.

Table 8: Crop illumination LED lamp data (from RUCOLA Antarctica demonstrator lamp)

Parameter	Power [W]
DC power to the lamp	100
DC/DC power supply power loss	6.0
DC voltage to DC current power loss	8.4
LED conversion power loss	35.7
LED optics power loss	4.0
Light spillage power loss	6.4
Power to cold plate	54.1
Power to growth chamber	45.9

3 Flight System Operations

The RUCOLA system is a complex equipment composed of several modules as follow (see Chapter 2):

1. Power, Command and Data Handling (PC&DH) Drawer.
2. Nutrient Management System (NMS) Drawer. It includes:
 - a. the Nutrient Distribution System (NDS)
 - b. the Microbial Contamination Control Module (MCCM) portion related to reduction of contamination in the liquid loops.
3. Growth Chamber Module (GCM) Drawer. It includes:
 - a. the Root Module (RM)
 - b. the Growth Chamber Atmosphere Control Module (GC-ACM)
 - c. the Gas Exchange Module (GEM)
 - d. the MCCM portion related to reduction of contamination in the growth chamber air loop)
4. Illumination System Drawer (ILS). It includes:
 - a. The lighting module
 - b. A High Definition camera
5. Microbial Monitoring System (MMS) Drawer. It includes:
 - a. The technologies for specific and a-specific selected microbial monitoring solutions)

These modules are aimed at the provision of all the functionalities needed for plant growth in a closed environment, as tested in the EDEN ISS project. They have to be uploaded on board of the ISS, configured and the installed in pre-defined location of the European Drawer Rack MKII (EDR MKII) inside Columbus, the European module of the International Space Station. The EDR MKII will provide not only the mechanical interfaces, but also the power, cooling and communication services as required for the RUCOLA Rack Operations. That requires the connection of the RUCOLA modules to the EDR MKII power/data connectors and to the water cooling system. Figure 6 and Figure 7 show all the interface possibilities.

Figure 6: EDR MKII Upper Interfaces

Figure 7: EDR MKII Services Interfaces

Apart from these connections, other connections have to be made for the correct functioning of the systems. All the RUCOLA rack S/S have to be connected to the PC&DH for electrical power distribution and for the management of all the sensors and actuators. The Root modules have to be connected to the Nutrient Delivery System, for the correct circulation of the nutrient solution.

All the connections will be done by means of cables and hoses on the front part of the equipment exactly as done for the ISPR RUCOLA Rack deployed in the MTF for the Antarctica operations.

3.1 RUCOLA Flight Operations Flow

Figure 8: Rucola Flight Operations Flow

The **operations flow** (from installation to end-of-life) of the RUCOLA system is identified in Figure 8. The flow includes mission preparation, mission execution and mission post-processing operations. This chapter focuses on the mission execution operations, with the scope of providing input for the identification of related design constraints and safety issues. Nevertheless a chapter dedicated to the possible failures will be also provided in order to identify in advance those countermeasures that can be implemented in the design phase..

The mission execution operations are divided into the following subgroups (addressed in the following sections):

- Commissioning operations (incl. HW unpacking, installation and functional check out)
- Nominal operations (incl. growth cycle start-up/seeding, growth follow-on, routine sampling management, crop harvest and processing, system re-conditioning, and assuming planned consumables replacement is contained within some of the just mentioned operations)
- Extraordinary maintenance operations (incl. HW failures management, crop-related issues management)

3.2 RUCOLA Commissioning

The commissioning is done in two main consecutive phases as described below.

3.2.1 Phase 1: HW unpacking and installation

The P/L HW is removed from the cargo containers/bags and inspected to identify all parts availability and any visible damage.

The P/L HW is then installed within EDR MKII rack. The installation includes mechanical assembly (within each experiment insert as well as experimental inserts within EDR MKII rack) as well as connection of electrical (power/data) and fluidic interfaces.

The crew, with a voice support of the ground operators, will do all this activity.

Operation Key Steps

1. Retrieve all the P/L HW cargo containers/bags from stowage
2. Retrieve all the P/L HW installation tools
3. Open cargo containers/bag A and identify/inspect the following assemblies:
 1. Power, Command and Data Handling drawer (inspect for visible damage)
 2. Power and data cables (inspect for visible damage)
4. Install power, command and data handling drawer in EDR MKII
5. Open cargo containers/bag B and identify/inspect the following assemblies:
 1. Nutrient Management System drawer (inspect for visible damage and DI water leakage)
 2. Concentrated nutrients bag (inspect for visible damage and salts leakage)
 3. Concentrated acid bag (inspect for visible damage and liquid leakage)
 4. Concentrated nutrients bag filling tool (inspect for visible damage)
 5. Fluidic cables (inspect for visible damage)
6. Add DI water from ISS water dispenser to the concentrated nutrients bag with the concentrated nutrients bag filling tool
7. Install concentrated nutrients bag in the Nutrient Management System drawer
8. Install concentrated acid bag in the Nutrient Management System drawer
9. Install Nutrient Management System drawer in rack EDR MKII
10. Open cargo containers/bag C and identify/inspect the following assemblies:
 1. Growth Chamber System drawer (inspect for visible damage)
 2. Root module insert, incl. "pre-seeded" plants (inspect for visible damage of all levels of containment and for signs of microbial contamination)
11. Install Growth Chamber drawer in rack EDR MKII
12. Open cargo containers/bag D and identify/inspect the following assemblies:
 1. Illumination System drawer (inspect for visible damage)
 2. Illumination System drawer cooling lines (inspect for visible damage)
 3. Illumination System drawer power/data cables (inspect for visible damage)
13. Install Illumination System drawer in rack EDR MKII
14. Open cargo containers/bag E and identify/inspect the following assemblies:
 1. Microbial Monitoring System drawer (inspect for visible damage)
 2. Microbial Monitoring System reagent inserts (inspect for visible damage or reagent leakage)
 3. Microbial Monitoring System drawer power/data cables (inspect for visible damage)

15. Install Microbial Monitoring System drawer
16. Install Microbial Monitoring System reagent inserts into microbial monitoring drawer
17. Switch on the Main Power Switch

3.2.2 Phase 2: HW functional check out

Once the crew activities has been completed the HW setup, the P/L HW is then activated and put into “HW functional check-out” configuration A minimum support will be requested to crew in this phase, in order to minimize the crew time as much as possible. The P/L SW “HW functional check out” function is used, with commands received from remote site) The check-out will be undergone at first at process-specific module level, and then at system level.

Operation Key Steps

1. Power, Command and Data Handling drawer check-out from remote for basic functionality (e.g. commands processing, telemetry upload, functional parameters within nominal behaviour, etc.) – this will provide basic information to subsequent modules and system check-out activities
2. Illumination System check-out from remote for basic functionality (e.g. commands processing, telemetry upload, functional parameters within nominal behaviour, etc.)
3. Illumination System detailed check-out with hand held PAR sensor for mapping of illumination within the empty growth chamber
4. Growth Chamber Module (GCM) check-out from remote for basic functionality (e.g. telemetry upload, functional parameters within nominal behaviour, etc.)
5. Gas Exchange Module (GEM) check-out from remote for basic functionality (e.g. commands processing, telemetry upload, functional parameters within nominal behaviour, etc.)
6. Nutrient Module (NM) check-out from remote for basic functionality (e.g. commands processing, telemetry upload, functional parameters within nominal behaviour, etc.)
7. Root Module (RM) check-out from remote for basic functionality (e.g. commands processing, telemetry upload, functional parameters within nominal behaviour, etc.)
8. Microbial Contamination Control Module (MCCM) check-out from remote for basic functionality (e.g. commands processing, telemetry upload, functional parameters within nominal behaviour, etc.)
9. MCCM air monitoring module detailed check-out with injection of relevant samples for analysis
10. MCCM nutrient solution monitoring module detailed check-out with injection of relevant samples for analysis
11. MCCM air contamination control module detailed check-out with monitoring module analysis after injection of relevant samples
12. MCCM nutrient solution contamination control module detailed check-out with monitoring module analysis after injection of relevant samples
13. ISPR System check-out from remote for integrated system functionality

3.3 Nominal Operations

The following activities fall in Nominal Operations category:

- Growth cycle start-up/seeding.
- Experiment follow-on.
- Routine sampling
- Crop harvest and processing
- System re-conditioning.

3.3.1 Growth cycle start-up/seeding

The P/L HW is put into “Operational” configuration. This includes the preparation of the Rack for a plant growth cycle, including the seedling phase (positioning of the root module pre-seeded insert/s), and the setting of the ambient parameters and of the irrigation cycles.

Operation Key Steps

1. Install root module pre-seeded insert/s in growth chamber drawer by removing the external level of containment just before sealing the growth chamber environment
2. Activate the rack
3. Configure the growth cycle parameters (temperature, Relative Humidity, CO2 level, O2 level, light intensity and composition, etc)
4. Configure the nutrient delivery system (nutrient solution composition, nutrient solution pH and EC, irrigation cycle, etc.)
5. Start the operations

3.3.2 Experiment follow-on

A daily check of the plants status is required for early identification of stress signals and definition of corrective actions as necessary (as for example the illumination level, increase/decrease the irrigation frequency or amount of nutrients delivered, etc.). In addition the monitoring of system performance will allow for early identification of malfunctions and anomaly resolution. The activities are mainly done by ground operators by means of telemetry and images analysis. Nevertheless crew can be involved for some specific check not possible from ground, like as for example root zone inspection. Other cases could require a crew intervention, like for example a visual inspection of plants in case the images are not clear enough to determine the presence of a problem.

Operation Key Steps

1. Telemetry analysis. Every day a ground operator has to check the telemetry values
2. Images analysis. Every day the ground operator has to collect and analyse plants images. The rack is put observation mode (it properly sets intensity and wavelength of the LED lights), images are taken of the plants and analysed to assess:
 - Status of the shoot zone growth (e.g. shoots presence, leaves number, leaves colour)
 - Evidence on microbial contamination on any visible surface of the growth chamberImage analysis will also allow for:
 - Visible leakage of liquids in the growth chamber
 - Visible floating particles in the growth chamber
3. During the plant growth phase, crew could be requested to daily check for visible leakage of liquids outside of ISPR.

3.3.3 Routine sampling.

Samples have to be periodically periodically collected and processed according to the experiment applicable plan. Samples may include liquids (nutrient solution, recovered condensate), gas (air from shoot zone), crop, various surfaces swabs. Processing may include immediate analysis (visual or with tools) and storage for late/ground analysis. This activities require a full involvement of crew, i.e. cannot be done by ground operators.

Operation Key Steps

1. Collect and analyse a concentrated nutrient solution sample; record results
2. Collect and analyse a diluted nutrient solution sample; record results
3. Collect and analyse a DI water sample; record results
4. Collect and analyse a recovered condensate water sample; record results
5. Collect and analyse a growth chamber surface swab samples (TBD number in TBD positions); record results
6. Collect and analyse* a leaf/fruit sample; record results
7. Collect, pack, label and freeze a leaf/fruit sample;

**In EDEN ISS Quality and Safety analysis of leaf/fruit samples are done using several tools. As example penetrometer, colorimeter analysis aimed at the verification of quality properties of the edible part of the plants. Another example is the Safety Analysis Using the Micro Biological Survey Method and available reagents, aimed at ensuring that the edible part of the plant can be safely eaten by the crew, i.e. no dangerous microorganism are present on the harvested samples. The possibility to use the same methodologies on board of the ISS has to be verified. Some instruments like penetrometer, colorimeter, Chlorophyll Meter could be used as they are. Others instruments, like for example those for Food Safety Analysis can pose safety threats to be deeply assessed before their upload on board. However a safety analysis is out of the scope of this document, therefore we assume that all the required analysis will be done in some way.*

3.3.4 Crop harvest and processing

This activity is aimed at harvesting leaves/fruits at the end if the plant growth cycle. It is a pure crew activity, having the objective to collect leaves and/or fruits and to prepare them for on ground analysis.

Operation Key Steps

1. Stop the ISPR operations and deactivate it
2. Open the Growth Chamber Module and harvest the leaves/fruits
3. Prepare leaves/fruits for download (store in labelled bag, freeze and store the bags for download)

3.3.5 System re-conditioning

The P/L HW is put into “Dormancy” configuration. This includes removal/cleaning of reservoirs as a minimum, but the following additional operations can be also included: inspection and cleaning (if necessary) of the growth chamber, replacement of consumables (e.g. filters), reconfiguration of the rack if a new plant growth cycle is foreseen.

Operations Key Steps

1. Identify and prepare all P/L re-conditioning tools
2. Remove, contain and dispose depleted concentrated nutrient solution bags
3. Remove, contain and dispose depleted concentrated acid bags
4. Open growth chamber

5. Visually inspect the growth chamber looking at and recording the following (take pictures when relevant):
 1. Evidence on microbial contamination on any visible surface of the growth chamber
 2. Visible leakage of liquids in the growth chamber
 3. Visible floating particles in the growth chamber
6. Clean all internal surfaces
7. Reconfigure the Growth chamber if a new growth cycle is foreseen, otherwise seal growth chamber.
8. Open cargo containers/bag E and identify/inspect the following assemblies:
 1. Microbial monitoring reagent inserts (inspect for visible damage or reagent leakage)
9. Replace microbial monitoring reagent inserts into microbial monitoring drawer

3.4 Failure Analysis

Plant cultivation on board of ISS represents a very challenging objective. Plants can suffer for several problems even if the system is working perfectly. Therefore in the failure analysis, with together the system anomalies, also the crop related issues have to be considered and managed.

In this chapter, a list of possible failure for both will be provided, with the objective to identify corrective action already in the design phase.

3.4.1 HW failures management

A list of potential HW failure scenarios is presented. For each scenario, a set of recovery actions is provided. The recovery actions range from component disabling/removal/exchange to more complex activities (e.g. cleaning surfaces, draining liquids, etc.).

Operation Key Steps

Table 9: Hardware failure analysis and management scenarios

System	Failure	Resolution	Impact on Design
Root Module	Sensors failures - Soil Moisture sensor inconsistent data - EC sensor inconsistent data	- Reset of the sensor Data Acquisition Unit (DAU) - Sensor replacement	- SW shall be designed in order to allow a DAU reset - Spare Sensor shall be available on board and easily replaceable
“	Solenoid valves not responding	- Power cycle of the valve - Valve replacement	- SW shall be designed in order to allow a valve reset - Spare valves shall be available on board and easily replaceable
“	Porous tube clogging	- Washing the tubes with distilled water - Replace the root Module	- the NDS shall be designed in order to permit the circulation of pure distilled water - Root Module spare (s) shall be available on board and easily installed/deinstalled

System	Failure	Resolution	Impact on Design
Root Module	Substrate microbial contamination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Medical treatments execution - Replacement of the Root Module 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Microbial contamination assessment shall be possible as much as possible without the intervention of crew - NDS shall be designed in order to allow medicine delivery to the substrate - The Root Module shall be designed in in order to contain the microbial contamination within it.
Nutrient Module	Sensors failure <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EC inconsistent data - pH inconsistent data - Temperature inconsistent data - Pressure inconsistent data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reset of the sensor Data Acquisition Unit (DAU) - Sensor replacement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SW shall be designed in order to allow a DAU reset - Spare Sensor shall be available on board and easily replaceable
“	Pump(s) Failure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pump power cycle - Pump replacement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SW shall be designed in order to allow a pump reset - Spare pumps shall be available on board and easily replaceable
“	Nutrient solution/water leakage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Connectors check - Tanks/bags replacement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tanks/bags shall be designed with a multiple containment in order to prevent severe lack of fluids
Microbial Contamination Control Module	Microbial monitoring unit failures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SW reset of the Unit - Replacement of the Unit 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SW shall be designed in order to allow the unit reset - Unit easily replaceable*
“	Actuator Failures <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pumps/s - Solenoid valves - UV unit 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Actuators reset - Actuators replacement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SW shall be designed in order to allow the unit reset - Actuators easily replaceable
“	- CFU filter	- Filter replacement	- Filter available on board and easily replaceable
LED Lamp Unit	Sensor Failures <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Temperature sensor - LED panel health sensor 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - LED Lamp Unit Power Cycle - LED Lamp Unit replacement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SW shall be designed in order to allow the unit reset - None (new unit to be uploaded on board)
“	LED lamp not nominal behaviour	- LED Lamp Unit Replacement	- None (new unit to be uploaded on board)
“	Leakage of cooling fluid	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Connectors check - LED Lamp Unit Replacement - Hoses Replacement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design shall consider a multiple containment of the leaked fluid - new unit to be uploaded on board
Growth Chamber Failure	Sensor(s) Failure <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pressure sensor inconsistent data - Oxygen sensor inconsistent data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reset of the sensor Data Acquisition Unit (DAU) - Sensor replacement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SW shall be designed in order to allow a DAU reset - Spare Sensor shall be available on board and easily replaceable

System	Failure	Resolution	Impact on Design
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Carbon dioxide sensor inconsistent data - Temperature sensor inconsistent data - Relative humidity sensor inconsistent data 		
“	Growth chamber surface microbial contamination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Medical treatments execution 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Growth Chamber shall be designed in order to contain the microbial contamination within it.
Gas Exchange Module	Sensor (s) Failures <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Temperature sensor inconsistent data - Relative humidity sensor inconsistent data - Air flow sensor inconsistent data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reset of the sensor Data Acquisition Unit (DAU) - Sensor replacement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SW shall be designed in order to allow a DAU reset - Spare Sensor shall be available on board and easily replaceable
“	Actuator Failures <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fan not nominal behaviour 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fan Reset - Fan replacement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SW shall be designed in order to allow the FAN reset and/or the change of the FAN speed - Spare fan shall be available on board and easily replaceable
“	Clogged filter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Filter replacement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Spare filter available on board and easily replaceable
Power, Command and data Handling Failure	Sensor Failures <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Temperature sensor inconsistent data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reset of the sensor Data Acquisition Unit (DAU) - Sensor replacement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SW shall be designed in order to allow a DAU reset - Spare Sensor shall be available on board and easily replaceable
“	Power conversion unit not nominal behavior	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Unit reset via command - Unit power cycle 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SW designed with a reset command
“	Data conversion unit not nominal behavior	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Unit reset via command - Unit power cycle 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SW designed with a reset command

Of course the list of the failures is not exhaustive, and represents only a first iterations of a refinement process that will evolve in parallel to the design and realization process. The list can change with the inclusion of new failures and/or new resolution methods. In any case this list is providing same operational requirements that impacts on the HW and SW design. the possibility to have commands for HW reset for example, is very important to allow ground operators to do a first attempt to solve the issue without the intervention of the crew. The possibility to easily replace some items is another very important point to be captured during the design phase.

Finally some requirements, like to have multiple containment, represent not only a design suggestion, but a safety constraints to be carefully taken into account since the beginning of the design process.

3.4.2 Crop-related issues management

A list of potential crop-related issues is presented. For each issue, a set of recovery actions is provided.

Table 10: Crop-related issues and design impact

Issue	Resolution	Impact on Design
Plant growth rate below expectations (e.g. delayed germination)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Change ambient parameters (T, RH, CO2, O2, light intensity, etc) via remote commands - Change of Nutrient Solution composition (EC, pH, T, etc) via remote commands - Change the irrigation frequency via remote commands - visual inspection of root and shoot zone by opening growth chamber, to define the best action - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SW shall allow the reception and routing of commands form ground operators - The Growth Chamber shall allow an easy access to the root module - The Root Module shall allow and easy and safe inspection of the root zone
Plant health issue detected: Signs of nutrient deficiency detected	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Change of Nutrient Solution composition (EC, pH, T, etc) via remote commands - Change the irrigation frequency via remote commands 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SW shall allow the reception and routing of commands form ground operators
Pest contamination detected (not yet visibly affecting plant health)	Medical treatment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Medical treatment should be possible without or minimizing the crew intervention (for example a system to spray medicine inside the closed growth chamber, to avoid crew and ISS ambient exposure to it)
Plant health issue detected: Signs of microbial contamination detected	Root Module removal and sanitization of the growth chamber	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Safe sanitization tools and methodology to be implemented by design (for example a system to spray medicine inside the closed growth chamber, to avoid crew and ISS ambient exposure to it) - Root module easily removable - Ziplock sealed bags to waste the affected plants
Plant health issue detected: signs of pest-induced damage detected	Root Module removal and sanitization of the growth chamber	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Safe sanitization tools and methodology to be implemented by design (for example a system to spray medicine inside the closed growth chamber, to avoid crew and ISS ambient exposure to it) - Root module easily removable <p>Ziplock sealed bags to waste the affected plants</p>

As for the system failure, more information’s will be gathered during the project evolution, leading to new possible issues and to new and maybe more efficient recovery action. Nevertheless, this short analysis of the plant issue is providing very important requirements for the payload design and most of all is posing several safety alert to be deeply investigated and addressed to the safety analysis. The possibility for crew to come in touch with possible treats appears to be quite probable.

4 Operations Products

This section describes the products to be used for on board operations and the related development processes, under the assumption that the RUCOLA Rack is an ESA experiments hosted in ESA facilities and operated under ESA responsibility.

4.1 Payload Operational Data File (PODF) - Definitions

As per [RD1], all tasks performed by the astronauts on-board the International Space Station (ISS) and by ground controllers in Mission and User Control Centres, from operation and maintenance of station systems to the execution of scientific experiments or high risk visiting vehicles docking manoeuvres, are performed according to procedures. In the ISS jargon those procedures are called Operations Data Files (ODF). ODFs can be seen as the 'user manuals' of the Space Station and can have multiple faces, going from traditional step-by-step procedures, scripts, cue cards, over displays, to software which guides the crew through the execution of nearly all tasks.

Due to the complexity of the ISS and despite the intensive training of the astronauts, well-developed Operations Data Files are the key to successful usage of space resources and the driving force behind the International Space Station operations.

According the ODF standard [RD 3] the procedures can be categorized as follow:

Activation and Checkout (A&C) procedures – Procedures used to activate, power-up, and checkout systems or individual subsystem components. That includes the first activation and checkout as well as activation and checkout of components after a power down.

Nominal operations procedures – Procedures used to carry out day-to-day operations of the systems or individual subsystem components. Preventative maintenance procedures and periodic maintenance procedures are included as nominal operations procedures to ensure continued satisfactory performance of these systems.

Malfunction procedures – Procedures designed to cope with system or equipment failure requiring a diagnostic process to determine the nature of the failure and possible corrective action (troubleshooting activities)). If normal conditions cannot be restored, the extent of degradation and the effects on subsequent operations must also be assessed. These procedures are not normally considered time critical; however, they generally should be performed as soon as possible.

Corrective procedures – Corrective procedures are designed to bypass or overcome a failure condition. They permit continued system's operations when a nominal means of continued support is no longer possible. These procedures are not normally considered time critical; however, they should be performed as soon as possible. Corrective procedures are sometimes associated with a malfunction procedure. Malfunction procedures are used to initiate problem diagnosis and implement temporary reconfigurations. Corrective procedures are subsequently used to recover available functionality from failed or degraded equipment. Corrective maintenance procedures are performed to restore system hardware integrity following anomalies or equipment problems encountered during system operations or as a result of conditions discovered during preventative maintenance. The primary method of corrective maintenance is removal and replacement. Contingency maintenance is a subset of corrective maintenance and is performed when the primary mode of corrective maintenance, removal and replacement, is not an option. Contingency maintenance is performed by repairing or reconfiguring data, power, or fluid lines to enable system operation. It may also involve the temporary repair of a system or component to restore functionality.

Alternate nominal procedures – Procedures which accomplish a known payload or system configuration or objective using a sequence of steps that is different from the sequence desired the majority of the time. This different sequence is used based on criteria established by the procedure writer

and/or science user and is well understood in advance to be a needed sequence for a significant minority of operations. Alternate procedures do not require additional resources, but may require a change request in order to have the specific procedure identified in the on board activities plan.

From operations entity point of view two procedures categories are defined:

- Crew procedures: Procedures used by the ISS crew member for the on-board operations
- Ground procedures – Procedures to operate systems or payloads from control centers or tele-science centers.

4.2 ESA PODF development and approval process

As per RD[1], the ESA ODF development process consists of three consecutive phases as depicted in Figure 9

Figure 9: ESA PODF Development Phases

Phase 0 is an hardware or experiment owner internal authoring, review, maturation and validation phase handled and managed by the ODF procedure author in close cooperation with the Payload or System Integration Managers and Industry to ensure technical feasibility of the activity, and the compliance of the ODF with standards, rules, and regulations. The Phase 0 ends with a validation process, by which the product is checked that it conforms to standards, meets safety requirements, and meets functional and operational effectiveness aspects. All PODF procedures should be validated in the highest-level facility available: desktop validation (low fidelity), Engineering or Training Model validations (high fidelity), Simulation Facility validation (high fidelity), or Flight Equipment validation (very high fidelity).

Phase 1 is the Change Request (CR) review phase, to be initiated by the ODF procedure author, but under responsibility of the ESA ODF Manager. ESA assigns mandatory and optional reviewers for the procedure and organizes a close-out panel to conclude on the dispositions from the different reviewers. When the procedure has been reviewed and passed the close-out panel it is delivered as final ODF procedure to the Columbus Control Centre (COL-CC). Typically once a month ESA ODF Management delivers an IPV package to COL-CC for upload. Exceptionally ODF procedures can be delivered outside a package as Fast Delivery or Event Driven Delivery (EDD).

Phase 2 is the last phase in the process and includes the on-console check and upload to the IPV Flight Library at NASA/JSC, under responsibility of COL-CC.

Figure 10: ESA PODF Development Timeline

Figure 10 shows the nominal (or ‘ideal’) development timeline for an ESA ODF. All development ‘milestones’ are related to the start of the ISS Increment during which the ODF procedure is foreseen to be executed. 6 months in advance a draft version is required for Crew and Ground Training (the training activity, in turn, often results in significant improvements and modifications to the procedures), 3 to 4 months in advance the ODF will be completely reviewed by reviewers with the relevant technical and operational background (typically a two-week review period, concluded with a close-out panel) and one month in advance the ODF should be ready for final publication. As mentioned before, Figure 5 shows the ‘ideal’ timeline, in reality ODFs are sometimes developed only very close to the execution date (because late readiness of experiment hardware or updates of procedures due to on-board anomalies, etc.) and expedite review and fast delivery processes are put in place to enable having certain ODF products on-board in a much shorter timeframe.

4.3 RUCOLA flight procedures preliminary list

The ISPR RUCOLA Rack procedures have to be prepared according the standard and the process defined in the previous chapters 5.1 and 5.2. According the process defined in Figure 9 and Figure 10 we are pretty far from the possibility to start the procedures development. Nevertheless, a preliminary list of the ISPR RUCOLA Rack for the on board operations can be derived from the list of potential ISPR RUCOLA Rack activities as described in Chapter 3, and from the procedures prepared for the EDEN ISS Antarctica Mission as described in [AD 2] and [AD 3]. The following table provide the results of such analysis.

Table 11: Preliminary List of RUCOLA Flight System PODF

Number	Procedure Title	Category	Operator
1.120	ISPR RUCOLA Rack Configuration	Activation &Checkout	Crew
1.140	ISPR RUCOLA Rack Activation and Check-out	Activation &Checkout	Crew/Ground
2.110	ISPR RUCOLA Rack Configuration for Plant Growth <i>(include seedling)*</i>	Nominal	Crew/Ground
2.120	ISPR RUCOLA Rack Performance and Crop Monitoring	Nominal	Crew/Ground
2.120	ISPR RUCOLA Rack Crop Harvesting	Nominal	Crew
2.130	Samples Collection and Storage for Safety Analysis	Nominal	Crew
2.210	Sample Collection and Storage for Quality Analysis	Nominal	Crew
2.220	Sample Collection and Storage for Safety Analysis	Nominal	Crew
2.230	Microbial Sampling	Nominal	Crew
2.310	ISPR RUCOLA Subsystems inspection	Nominal	Crew
2.320	ISPR RUCOLA CO2 Bottle Replacement	Nominal	Crew
2.330	ISPR RUCOLA NDS Tanks Water Refill	Nominal	Crew
2.340	ISPR RUCOLA NDS Tanks Waste Water Emptying	Nominal	Crew
2.350	ISPR RUCOLA NDS Concentrated Nutrient Tanks Replacement	Nominal	Crew
2.410	ISPR RUCOLA Root Module Replacement	Nominal	Crew
3.100	ISPR RUCOLA Overtemperature/ Under-temperature management	Malfunction	Crew/Ground
3.200	ISPR RUCOLA Gas Exchange Module Failure Management	Malfunction	Crew/Ground
3.300	ISPR RUCOLA NDS Failure Management	Malfunction	Crew/Ground
3.400	ISPR RUCOLA Illumination System Failure	Malfunction	Crew/Ground

Number	Procedure Title	Category	Operator
	Management		
3.500	ISPR RUCOLA Root Module Failure Management	Malfunction	Crew/Ground
3.600	ISPR RUCOLA Growth Chamber Failure Management	Malfunction	Crew/Ground
3.700	ISPR RUCOLA Microbial Contamination Control Module Failure Management	Malfunction	Crew/Ground
3.800	ISPR RUCOLA Power, Command and Data Handling Module Failure Management	Malfunction	Crew/Ground
3.910	Plant Growth Rate Anomaly	Malfunction	Crew/Ground
3.920	Plant Health Issue Detection	Malfunction	Crew/Ground
3.930	Microbacterial Contamination Detection	Malfunction	Crew/Ground
4.100	ISPR RUCOLA S/S's Power Cycle	Corrective	Ground
4.200	ISPR RUCOLA Gas Exchange Module Sensors, Fans and Filters Replacement	Corrective	Crew
4.300	ISPR RUCOLA NDS Sensors, Pumps and Filters Replacement	Corrective	Crew
4.400	ISPR RUCOLA LED Lamp Unit Replacement	Corrective	Crew
4.500	ISPR RUCOLA Root Module Sensors and Valves Replacement	Corrective	Crew
4.600	ISPR RUCOLA Growth Chamber Sensors Replacement	Corrective	Crew
4.700	ISPR RUCOLA Microbial Contamination Control Module Sensors and Actuators Replacement	Corrective	Crew
4.800	ISPR RUCOLA Power, Command and Data Handling Module Relay's Replacement	Corrective	Crew

Of course, this list is not exhaustive and will be refined during the project phases as a normal consequence of a learning process associated with the evolution of the project itself.

The development process will be customized for the RUCOLA system operations preparation needs and different for the Crew and Ground operators procedures. In particular, under the assumption the ISPR RUCOLA Rack will be developed in three different models (Training, Engineering and Flight Models) we can preliminary plan the following:

Crew procedures

In order to deliver the procedure in time for crew training, a first level of validation (hereinafter called procedure verification) will be done by means of the Training Model @EAC as soon as the **draft** version of this procedure will be available. The objective of this working session is to test the sequence and to verify the correctness of the procedural steps and to collect the feedback coming from crew instructors. After this session the procedures will be updated, submitted to the Jira Desktop review and then released in their **preliminary** version. **Final** version will be validated by means of the Engineering Model integrated into the EDR MKII Engineering Model. The objective of this session is to validate the final sequence of the steps, the tool usage and finally the duration.

Ground procedures.

Three version of the procedures are envisaged, each of them with a different level of validation.

A **draft** version, based on the display layout will be proposed for the desktop review.

A **preliminary** version will be verified against the displays and the EM. The **final** version will be validated against the Engineering Model integrated in the EDR MKII EM and using the real operational environment as much as as possible. In other word, the procedures will be validated operating the ISPR RUCOLA Rack from the control room of the appointed User and Support Operations Center (USOC), as in the final and nominal ground segment configuration.

4.4 Human Computer Interfaces (Displays)

The RUCOLA Rack operations require the monitoring and control of the RUCOLA H&S and of the environmental parameters via dedicated SW, providing the capability to send commands and visualize the ISPR telemetries via dedicated Computer Interfaces (hereinafter called displays) on both ISS and remote control centre computers.

For the EDEN ISS operations the Labview SW has been used, and several displays have been developed. For the ISS operations we assume that the same SW can be used, but well defined standard and processes have to be considered for SW and displays acceptance as clearly defined in [RD5].

Similarly to procedures, a well defined standard has to be used for the displays layout. The standard serves to generate cohesive and integrated products for use in real-time operations and training.

In addition the ISS displays have to be approved by the Integrated Display and Graphics Standards (IDAGS) Panel prior to being integrated into a platform.

The IDAGS Panel reviews the displays for consistency with the standard and with other similar displays. Crew Office (or directly crew members) also take part to the display The results of the review is presented form the IDAGS Panel as action (approval, disapproval, approval with modifications).

It is worth to underline that this process runs in parallel to the procedures development process, even if it has to be completed earlier to allow the preparation of those procedures for computer based ISPR RUCOLA Rack operations.

As already done for the procedures, at this stage, from the Analysis of the operations scenario and what done during the EDEN ISS operations we can define a preliminary list of displays to be used for the RUCOLA Rack mission n board of the ISS as follow.

A main Displays will provide the capability to monitor the RUCOLA Rack main functionalities and the RUCOLA Rack to EDR MKII interfaces. Other displays will provide the TM monitoring capability for the all the RUCOLA subsystems:

- **Growth Chamber:** telemetry monitoring of the ambient parameters and images acquisition. commands for camera's configurations.
- **Nutrient module:** telemetry monitoring of the substrate status (Soil humidity, temperature, pH, EC) and to manually activate/deactivate the valves.
- **Illumination system:** telemetry monitoring, command to power on/off the lamp unit, to set light intensity, to define lighting cycle.
- **Nutrient Delivery System:** telemetry monitoring of the actuator status and sensors telemetry, on/off command to the actuators, definition of the composition of the nutrient solution and of the irrigation cycle
- **Power, Command and Data Handling:** telemetry monitoring of the critical parameters of the electronic boards (as for example current and voltage level of the power channels and boards temperatures). Command to power on/off the boards, or the subsystems, etc.
- **Microbial Contamination Control Module:** telemetry for sensors monitoring.
- **Gas Exchange Module:** telemetry for sensors monitoring, commands to actuators (Fans, valves, etc)

5 Ground Segment Layout for the RUCOLA Operations

The design of the RUCOLA Rack Ground Segment Layout shall take into account the general ESA Ground Segment Architecture and the consolidate roles of the involved Centers.

In fact being the RUCOLA Rack a class-2 P/L to be accommodated into the EDR MKII (next to be uploaded on board of COLUMBUS), the Ground Infrastructure for its operations has to consider the already existing part of the ESA Ground Segment and responsibilities defined for the Columbus operations.

5.1 Scenario for ISS in Europe: the decentralized approach

For the operations related to the ESA payloads on the ISS, the user support and payload operations infrastructure makes use of a decentralized architecture as described in Figure 11. In this setup, the most important entities are the Columbus Control Center (COL-CC) and the User Support Operations Centers (USOCs) that are connected to the European Network for ISS Operations via the Interconnected Ground Sub-network (IGS), which is a private, secure network running over dedicated Wide Area Network (WAN) with a central node located at Col-CC.

Figure 11: Overview of ISS/MSM Ground Segment for Columbus Operations.

The Wide Area Network Services (IGS-WAN) are based on VPN (Virtual Private Network) technology and include ESA relays located at international partner sites, IGS access nodes in Europe and data transport services, such as data voice and video for Columbus as well as for any other European ISS utilisation within the US Lab or the Russian Lab. The IGS provides the communications infrastructure

connecting the user centres for operations. The IGS includes management of the network to ensure proper end-to-end communications for the various centres. That is done at four different levels:

- the Data Services System (DaSS) represents a uniform interface to European users for the exchange of telemetry and telecommand, based as far as possible on CCSDS standards. It provides telemetry (raw and processed) distribution, user command handling services, as well as a demultiplexing service at the Columbus CCSDS Gateways at the international partner sites.
- The Columbus Decentralised Mission Control System (CD-MCS) is the control system delivered by ESA to the different User and Support Operations Centres (USOCs) for the operations conduction. The Columbus Ground Support (CGS) software is the basis for CD-MCS, and is delivered with different software for acquisition of telemetry and dispatching of commands using different protocols:
 - CD-MCS multicast,
 - raw packets over TCP
 - DaSS (Columbus Ground Segment specific protocol),
 - PaCTS (EGSE software used by some of the Columbus payloads).

Finally, the CD-MCS includes a suite for the implementation of graphical displays for TM visualization and TC management (USS Editor and USS Executor)

- the Voice Conferencing System (VoCS) provides access to any operational voice loops as well as to A/G and S/G loops. VoCS offers storage, archiving and retrieval of selected voice loops. Col-CC provides keysets for USOCs.
- the Video Distribution and Conferencing System (ViDS) supports the reception and distribution of ISS video to the USOCs via the IGS network. Users can retrieve video data from the Col-CC via file download / IP (Internet Protocol) streaming. Video conferencing services are offered for all ground segment sites.

In this network, the Columbus Control Centre (**COL-CC**), located at DLR/GSOC, Oberpfaffenhofen, Germany, is the responsible of the operations of the entire ESA segment on board of the ISS. Such a responsibility includes, among the other, the provision of the necessary co-ordination functions for the conduction of payload operations on the ISS for both the preparatory and the execution phase.

The Col-CC provides a point of contact to the partner's operations centres MCC-H (Mission Control Center – Houston), POIC (Payload Operations Integration Centre), MCC-M (Mission Control Centre – Moscow) for issues affecting the whole ESA payload complement. For other issues related to the ESA payloads located on the ISS the Col-CC co-ordinates responses with the operations management personnel.

The **USOCs** are the focal points for the preparation and the conduction of ESA payload operations. They play an important role in linking the science user community to the ISS utilisation. The centres are equipped with a set of ESA provided standard services, including the communications capabilities, i.e. the tools for the connection to the IGS network and the conduction of the operations. Moreover they are provided with the Engineering Models (EMs) and Science Reference Models (SRMs) for the preparation of the operations, validation of the operations products, and the execution of parallel ground experiments for training purpose or for baseline data collection.

External entities can be connected to the IGS network to support the operations from the engineering and scientific point of view. Dedicated centers named User Home Base's (**UHB's**) can be connected to the USOC via secure connection over the Public Internet (Virtual Private Networks), and provided with the access to all the operational tools and services, including those for TM/TC processing. In general, the UHB's are equipped with standard COTS HW plus Agency Furnished Equipment (so called UHB Terminal SW and USS Executor SW). In addition they can be provided with the same dis-

plays used by the USOC’s operators (developed to be used via USS executor) able to offer user friendly way for telemetry monitoring and commanding.

With this capability, the Science team can manage and orient the experiment, the Engineering Support team can continuously monitor Telemetry and can provide feedback on the system (subsystems) performances.

5.2 RUCOLA Experiment Ground Segment Architecture

The RUCOLA GS architecture shall be based on CDMCS cascading connection as per ESA baseline ground segment architecture. In this scenario, the EDR II USOC is connected to COL-CC through CDMCS over IGS network and, as shown in Figure 12, is configured to manage not only the TM/TC data flow, in both operational and simulation environment via the so-called Ops LAN, but also communication exchange via the so-called OPS Support LAN.

The UHB’s will be connected to the OPS-SUP-LAN network only via VPN (over public internet), with the EDR II USOC EXT-FW (External Firewall) acting as VPN Gateway. Authentication is provided by certificates (one for each client workstation) released by the USOC itself using the ESA Certification Authority.

Figure 12: USOC Possible Architecture

Figure 13: ISPR RUCOLA Rack Ground Segment Hierarchy

Two UHB's could be foreseen for the RUCOLA Experiment. The first (TAS-I Torino) will provide Engineering Support, the second (To be defined) will provide scientific support. The above Figure 13 shows the logical structure of how the different centers can be linked together for the RUCOLA Experiment.

The CDMCS server will provides the EDR II USOC with the capability to forward the received ISPR RUCOLA Rack and EDR II TM to the UHB's for experiment and RUCOLA system real time monitoring

CDMCS can also accept commands from the UHB's to configure the ISPR RUCOLA Rack, and that represent the desired scenario. Nevertheless such a possibility has to be negotiated with ESA, since the ESA policy is to assign the commanding capability to the only entity on the IGS Network (COL CC and USOC's).

As said, The TM/TC can be managed and the scientific data/images can be managed using the Agency furnished tools, and the displays developed using the CD-MCS suite.

Nevertheless for the RUCOLA experiment, it will be proposed to use, according to what done for the EDEN ISS operations, an ad –hoc developed SW based on the LABVIEW suite. That will require the development of a SW with the capability to connect this SW to the CDMCS environment, providing the capability to the UHB's to use the same tool used during the ground activities in preparation of the flight hardware, for example during the AIT phase, or during the ground experiments. The idea is not only to export to the UHB's operations something used during the development phase, but to provide a common tool to the Engineer Support Team, to the crew for the onboard operations and to the USOC for the ground operators, to facilitate and speed up the operations, especially in the critical phases.

6 RUCOLA Preliminary ISS Operation Conclusions

The upload of the RUCOLA Rack on board of the ISS, requires several steps that includes not only the upgrade of the HW and SW developed for the EDEN ISS project.

Besides them, the operations preparatory activities have to be taken into account. They includes the preparation of the operational products, and the setup of the operations ground network, with a clear definition of the role and responsibility, and of the equipment and tools to be used.

In EDEN ISS project the capability to work with ODF like procedures has been tested, with the procedures developed using standard and processes similar to those used for the ISS operations, and a SW application has been developed to distribute different kind of data and images coming from different sources, including those generated by the RUCOLA SW.

However, what implemented for the EDEN ISS project cannot be exported directly in the ISS operations.

That will require a very demanding effort to be done in parallel to the HW and SW upgrade. But before the definition of a clear development program and the baseline of technical solutions is needed. In fact, that represents the first level of inputs to correctly derive the operative products and the ground segment configuration.

At time, the development program is not yet started, the technical solutions not yet baselined, and therefore it make no sense to upgrade the procedures and the tools used for the EDEN ISS operations for ISS operations. Also the definition of a development plan is not possible.

Nevertheless, starting from the results obtained during the EDEN ISS test campaign, and from the former experience of TPZ as ESA USOC, it was possible to define a high level scenario, and to define the sequence of activities to be done on board, and the associated products. Moreover it was possible to identify a possible architecture of the ground network that has to be implemented to support the RUCOLA Experiment on-board operations.

7 Key highlights for growing plants on-board ISS

LIT's focus in this work package was on all relevant aspects relating to growing plants on-board ISS. This included the investigation of plant growth characteristics under microgravity for the selected plants, estimating the produced food and waste and defining measures to assure food quality and safety.

7.1 General factors affecting plant growth

There are several factors attributable to successful crop growth that are not only applicable to terrestrial cultivation but become of greater importance when investigating non-terrestrial production. Each of these factors have significant roles in ensuring reliable crop output and often have negative consequences with respect to crop quality and safety when mismanaged. Fundamental factors that require consideration are:

- Effect of Space Environment (Microgravity impact on plant physiology and metabolism)
- Root management and stability
- Nutrient management
- Illumination
- Environmental management
- Contamination control

These factors were considered as part of this project; with the implementation of the RUCOLA rack through the development of dedicated hardware modules as described previously. Due to issues with the bespoke root modules, it was not possible for TASI to provide a module to LIT for dedicated growth studies. Therefore, LIT were reliant on data and samples to be provided from the RUCOLA module based on the EDEN ISS Mobile Test Facility at the Neumeyer III site. However, LIT endeavoured to fulfil its commitment to this work package by attempting to retrofit an Orbitec porous tube nutrient delivery system (Figure 14).

Figure 14: Orbitec plant growth system (left) with internal porous NDS tubes (right)

Unfortunately, the upper containment section could not be utilised due to power management and software compatibility issues. Attempts were made to utilise the NDS trays with rockwool as a substrate. The aim was to employ the trays for general rooting but have them sit individually within LITs growth chamber facility—effectively using the larger chamber for the environmental contribution and illumination. While every effort was made to utilise these trays in conjunction with available clinostats for microgravity testing, the inability to control nutrient solution supply to the trays due to solenoid valve issues forced the abandonment of these investigative attempts.

7.2 Crop output under microgravity conditions

As per section 7.1 due to the unavailability of the Rucola rooting module and failure to retrofit Orbitec modules to complete the dedicated growth study, it was not possible to complete microgravity studies on the clinostats as the configuration of the Orbitec modules, the rotational aspect of the clinostats did not allow for stable operation of the module.

7.3 Quality and safety on-board ISS

As part of work packages 4 and 5, qualitative and semi quantitative methods of food quality and safety were developed by LIT and tested on the EDEN ISS Mobile Test Facility at the Neumeyer III site. These methods utilise five hand held devices include the following:

- a. Colourimeter – Measured colour of fruit as an indication of bioactive and nutraceutical value;
- b. Penetrometer – Firmness of fruit as an indication of ripeness (Figure 15);
- c. Nitrate Ion Selective Electrode – In-situ antinutritional indicator (range of edible Nitrate) in salad crops;
- d. Chlorophyll – Indication of plant health and bioactive value;
- e. %Brix Meter – Indication of % sugar in fruit and vegetable.

Figure 155: Examples of Penetrometer (left) and Chlorophyll Meter (right) in use

It is our experience and recommendation that these hand held devices can transition for use on the ISS considering sample preparation requirements for the Nitrate and %Brix meter which require food samples to be homogenised in water before measurement can be carried out.

Overall results and recommendations relating to these handheld devices and be reviewed in Deliverable 5.7 of the EDEN ISS Final Mission Report.

An estimation of food quality and mass and waste produced from these small-scale growth systems could not be determined as a result of the issues faced by module design and operation. Due to the lack of sample from the RUCOLA module, LIT were unable to compare any potential quality and safety impacts that may be experienced using the RUCOLA module to those identified from the FEG data obtained during mission operations.

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